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Iron Losses of Dual-Star PMSMs with Open-Circuit Fault under Fault-Tolerant Control

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Abstract—In this paper the iron losses of dual-star permanent-magnet synchronous machines under fault-tolerant control with phase open-circuit fault are investigated. Various faults including one or two open-circuits in different phases are considered. The iron loss terms, namely hysteresis, eddy-current, anomalous, and rotational losses, considering harmonics are calculated based on *a priori* knowledge of magnetic field distribution obtained by magnetostatic FE simulations. A variety of motor topologies including laminated-core surface-mounted or interior permanent magnet with distributed or concentrated winding are studied. As far as the core losses are concerned, it is observed that the machines are ill-conditioned under the post-fault control, i.e. the iron losses considerably increase, particularly at high speeds. Moreover, in contrast to the healthy case, the iron losses will not be distributed evenly among the stator teeth which leads to concentration of loss in some segments of the core.

Index Terms—fault-tolerant control, iron losses, permanent-magnet synchronous machines, multi-phase machines

I. INTRODUCTION

Introduction of electrical machines into applications where reliability and safety are essential has prompted the development of fault-tolerant electrical drives in recent decades [1], e.g. in automotive [2] and aerospace industry [3]. Thanks to higher redundancy, multi-phase electrical drives are an interesting option in this regard [4]. The dual-star winding diagram, otherwise known as asymmetrical six phase, is of special interest as it can be supplied together with three-phase off-the-shelf inverters. Moreover, dual-star machines can provide slightly higher torque with lower torque ripple compared to their three-phase counterparts [5].

Phase open-circuit (PhOC) is one of the most common faults in electrical drives [6], [7]. Therefore, corresponding remedial actions are required in order to keep the drive optimally operational. A simple solution in dual-star drives consists in disconnecting the faulty star. Alternatively, only the faulty phase can be isolated and fault-tolerant control (FTC) methods can be adopted. While with only one functional star almost half of nominal torque can be generated, the latter approach gives higher torque without violating the thermal constraints.

When PhOC(s) occurs, the phase currents should be modified for reducing the extra torque ripple caused by the fault. In

order to find proper currents, the FTC strategy is usually formulated as an optimization problem where the phase currents (amplitude and phase or instantaneous value) are degrees of freedom and minimizing torque ripple, maximizing the torque, and/or minimizing phase or total copper loss are the objectives [8]–[12].

FTC methods are based on the assumption that core losses will not be affected by them. However, in practice, the field distribution in the machine core with PhOCs even under fault-tolerant control strategies is distorted. Hence, iron losses may increase under post-fault operation and contribute to the temperature increase in machine besides the copper loss, particularly in high speed or flux weakening region.

This paper aims to cast light on the losses in magnetic core and PMs of a dual-star tooth-wound interior PMSM under FTC strategy with different PhOC faults. The machine under study is designed for electric power-assisted steering system in cars [5]. Moreover, other machine topologies with surface-mounted or interior PMs and distributed winding stator derived from the original machine are studied. All iron losses terms including hysteresis, eddy-current (EC), anomalous, and rotational ones are considered in the magnetic steel.

In the next section, the original machine as well as the derived topologies are introduced. In Section III, the mathematical model of the machine is developed, and the FTC method for different number and location of PhOC faults adopted in this paper is presented. The method for the calculation of different terms of iron losses is briefly explained in Section IV. In Section V, the iron losses under post-fault operation with different PhOCs are calculated and compared with the healthy case. Then, the loss distribution under FTC is discussed in Section VI. Finally the paper is concluded in the last section.

II. PMSMS UNDER STUDY

The original machine is a tooth-wound interior (TWI) PMSM with 10 poles and 12 slots as shown in Fig. 1. Its rated voltage and current are 4 V_{rms} and 110 A_{rms}, respectively. The stator winding consists of two stars, namely, ABC1 and ABC2, shifted by 30° electrical. The current direction in each coil side is depicted by minus and plus signs. The neutrals are assumed to be connected, since higher torque under OC faults and FTC can be achieved compared to two isolated neutrals [11]. The machine parameters are reported in Table I. Moreover, three

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Fig. 1. Cross-section of the original dual-star PMSM

Fig. 2. Cross-section of adapted dual-star PMSM with DW stator and SPM rotor

PMSMs are derived from the original machine: tooth-wound surface-mounted (TWS), distributed-winding surface-mounted (DWS), and distributed-winding interior (DWI) PMSMs.

In Fig. 2, the PMSM with SPM rotor and DW is shown. The two other topologies use the same stators and similar rotors as shown in Fig. 1 and 2. With the surface-mounted PMs, the arc length of the PMs is adjusted for having low torque ripple as the original machine. Furthermore, the thickness of the PMs are selected to have comparable flux weakening capability as the original machines. With the DW stator, the design is adapted again for having comparable current density and rated voltage as the original machine. Hence, the number of parallel paths is changed to 5. Moreover, a full-pitch single-layer winding is adapted. The main dimensions including inner and outer diameters and axial length are as the original machine. The phase BEMF and torque of four PMSMs with q-axis current of 155 A obtained by FE simulations are shown in 3 and 4, respectively.

Fig. 3. Phase A BEMF with different stator and rotor topologies at 1000 rpm

Fig. 4. Torque with different stator and rotor topologies with q-axis current of 155 A

III. MACHINE MODEL AND FAULT-TOLERANT CONTROL STRATEGY

A. Machine model

The phase voltage equations are:

$$v_x = Ri_x + \frac{d\Psi_x}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where v_x , i_x and Ψ_x with $x \in \{A1, B1, C1, A2, B2, C2\}$ are phase voltages, currents, and flux linkages, respectively. Using the amplitude-invariant vector space decomposition (VSD) transformation [13], the abc variables can be transformed to three orthogonal sub-planes as follows:

TABLE I
SPECIFICATIONS OF THE PMSMs

	TWI	TWS	DWI	DWS
turns per coil	8	8	8	7
parallel paths	2	2	5	5
magnet remanence (T)	1.35	1.35	1.35	1.35
(min.) air gap (mm)	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.55
PM thickness (mm)	3	2	3	1.3
stack length (mm)	57	57	57	57
stator outer dia. (mm)	86.6	86.6	86.6	86.6
rotor outer dia. (mm)	50	50	50	50
yoke width (mm)	4	4	6	6
fill factor (%)	38	38	43	43
pole number	10	10	10	10
slot number	12	12	60	60

$$\begin{bmatrix} F_\alpha \\ F_\beta \\ F_{z1} \\ F_{z2} \\ F_{o1} \\ F_{o2} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{-1}{2} & \frac{-\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{-1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-1}{2} & \frac{-\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{-1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & 1 \\ 1 & \frac{-\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{-1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{-1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & \frac{-1}{2} & \frac{-\sqrt{3}}{2} & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} F_{A1} \\ F_{A2} \\ F_{C1} \\ F_{C2} \\ F_{B1} \\ F_{B2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where F stands for voltage, current, or flux-linkage. Applying (2) to (1) and assuming sinusoidally distributed windings, the corresponding voltage equations are:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_\alpha \\ v_\beta \end{bmatrix} = R \begin{bmatrix} i_\alpha \\ i_\beta \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} L_d^{\text{VSD}} & 0 \\ 0 & L_q^{\text{VSD}} \end{bmatrix} \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_\alpha \\ i_\beta \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{z1} \\ v_{z2} \end{bmatrix} = R \begin{bmatrix} i_{z1} \\ i_{z2} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} L_1 & 0 \\ 0 & L_1 \end{bmatrix} \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_{z1} \\ i_{z2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{o1} \\ v_{o2} \end{bmatrix} = R \begin{bmatrix} i_{o1} \\ i_{o2} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} L_1 & 0 \\ 0 & L_1 \end{bmatrix} \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_{o1} \\ i_{o2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

with L_d^{VSD} and L_q^{VSD} being equivalent d- and q-axis inductances, L_1 leakage inductance, and R the phase resistance. Assuming that the cross-coupling terms are compensated by the control [13], they are ignored in (3) to (4). Sub-plane $\alpha\beta$ contains the fundamental harmonic alongside harmonics of order $12k \pm 1$, sub-plane $z1z2$ $6k \pm 1$ harmonics, and sub-plane $o1o2$ $3k$ harmonics, where k is a positive non-zero integer. Only i_α and i_β contribute to the torque production, while the other currents cause extra copper loss. Therefore, in the healthy case, the reference currents in $z1z2$ and $o1o2$ are set to zero [13].

B. Fault-tolerant control strategy

The FTC method in this paper is adopted from [11], [12]. In the case of PhOC, (3) to (5) are still valid, although the currents in different sub-planes are not independent anymore. Therefore, unlike the healthy case, non-zero reference currents should be assigned for currents in $z1z2$ and $o1o2$ sub-planes. Since only i_α and i_β contribute to torque production, it is useful to write the currents as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_\alpha & i_\beta & i_{z1} & i_{z2} & i_{o1} & i_{o2} \end{bmatrix}^t = \mathbf{K} * \begin{bmatrix} i_\alpha & i_\beta \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the coefficient matrix:

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & K_{z1,\alpha} & K_{z2,\alpha} & K_{o1,\alpha} & K_{o2,\alpha} \\ 0 & 1 & K_{z1,\beta} & K_{z2,\beta} & K_{o1,\beta} & K_{o2,\beta} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (7)$$

where superscript T stands for the transpose operation.

The value of the coefficients depends on the number and location of OCs. Assuming a single isolated neutral point and imposing e.g. $i_A = 0$ in (2) and (6) yield:

$$K_{o1,\alpha} = -K_{o2,\alpha} = -1 - K_{z1,\alpha}, \quad K_{o1,\beta} = -K_{o2,\beta} = K_{z1,\beta} \quad (8)$$

Moreover, with one more PhOC, $K_{z2\alpha}$ and $K_{z2\beta}$ can be also written as a function of $K_{z1\alpha}$ and $K_{z1\beta}$. Depending on the second PhOC location, different expressions can be derived as reported in Table II.

The independent coefficients are found using an optimization problem where maximizing torque is the objective. All the coefficient values and expressions for different combinations of PhOC are reported in Table II. The other possible combinations of two PhOCs are redundant, i.e. under the same FTC strategy, they have the same effect in terms of torque and loss. Moreover, the rating factor RF , is defined as the ratio of maximum current in sub-plane $\alpha\beta$ to the rated phase current for which the phase current does not exceed the rated one. This factor is also reported in Table II.

IV. IRON LOSSES

Iron losses are calculated based on empirical formulas and *a priori* knowledge of the flux density distribution. FE implemented by open-source software ONELAB [14] is used for the computation of magnetic quantities. Moreover, the losses are calculated in frequency domain, which means the calculated losses are averaged over one electrical period. Total iron losses are separated into hysteresis loss, P_{hys} , eddy-current loss, P_{eddy} , and excess loss, P_{exc} [15]:

$$P_{\text{total}} = P_{\text{hys}} + P_{\text{eddy}} + P_{\text{exc}} \quad (9)$$

P_{hys} is calculated as:

$$P_{\text{hys}} = \alpha_{\text{hys}} \sum_{l=1}^{N_{\text{ele}}} B_{p,l}^\alpha f A_{\text{ele},l} \quad (10)$$

where N_{ele} is the number of mesh elements, $B_{p,l}$ the peak flux density in element l , $A_{\text{ele},l}$ the element area, and f the fundamental frequency. α_{hys} and the exponent α depends on the magnetic steel characteristics. It should be mentioned that the effect of minor-loop in hysteresis loss is ignored. The harmonics are not considered in (10) explicitly. However, using maximum value of flux density in elements takes account of harmonics to some extent.

P_{eddy} is calculated as:

$$p_{\text{eddy}} = \alpha_{\text{eddy}} \sum_{l=1}^{N_{\text{ele}}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 B_{n,l}^2 f^2 (1 + \alpha_1 B_{n,l}^{\alpha_2}) A_{\text{ele},l} \quad (11)$$

TABLE II
COEFFICIENT VALUES OR EXPRESSIONS IN (7) BASED ON MAXIMUM TORQUE STRATEGY WITH VARIOUS OC FAULTS

	A1	A1&A2	A1&C1	A1&C2	A1&B2
$K_{z1,\alpha}$	-0.641	-1	-0.5339	0	-1
$K_{z1,\beta}$	0.209	0	-0.2699	0.2679	0
$K_{z2,\alpha}$	0.754	$2 + \sqrt{3} + (2 - \sqrt{3})K_{z1,\alpha}$	$\sqrt{3}(1 + K_{z1,\alpha})$	$2 - \sqrt{3} + (2 + \sqrt{3})K_{z1,\alpha}$	$-1 - K_{z1,\alpha}$
$K_{z2,\beta}$	-0.295	$-1 + (2 - \sqrt{3})K_{z1,\beta}$	$(1 + \sqrt{3})K_{z1,\beta}$	$-1 + (2 + \sqrt{3})K_{z1,\beta}$	$-1 - K_{z1,\beta}$
$RF(\%)$	69.4	28.8	55.7	55.7	57.7

where n is the harmonic number of flux density waveform and α_{eddy} the eddy current loss coefficients. The term $(1 + \alpha_1 B_{n,i}^{\alpha_2})$ is for considering the increased EC losses due to the saturation [16]. P_{exc} is calculated as:

$$p_{exc} = \alpha_{exc} \sum_{l=1}^{N_{ele}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 B_{n,l}^{1.5} f^{1.5} A_{ele,l} \quad (12)$$

α_{exc} is excess loss coefficients. All of the unknowns in the equations (10) to (12) are obtained based on fitting the experimental loss data provided in the material data sheet with (10) assuming purely sinusoidal flux density. The curve fitting is defined as a least square problem. The obtained parameters are: $\alpha_{hyst} = 0.017$, $\alpha_{eddy} = 2.48 \times 10^{-5}$, $P_{exc} = 9.3 \times 10^{-5}$, $\alpha = 1.77$, $\alpha_1 = 2.494$, $\alpha_2 = 0.898$. It should be mentioned that better agreement between fitted curve and $P_{data,i}(B, f)$ is achieved with considering the effect of saturation in (11), (objective function value 0.3 vs. 0.89).

For considering the effect of flux density rotation on the losses, the flux density vector in elements for each harmonic is projected on the major and minor axes of the ellipse formed by the B-locus, and the losses are calculated for these two components separately [17].

V. IRON LOSSES IN HEALTHY AND FAULTY CASES

For the iron losses calculation, the FE model used for the computation of the flux density distribution is supplied by the reference currents obtained in section III. Moreover, the iron losses just for the speeds around and higher than the base one are calculated, since they assume importance at high speeds. The i_d and i_q currents for each operating point with given speed and torque are selected based on maximum torque per current (MTPA) strategy and flux weakening given the voltage limit [18]. The FE model is used for calculating the optimal currents for the MTPA and also required negative d-axis current for the flux weakening strategy.

The iron losses maps in torque-speed plane for different rotor topologies are shown in Fig. 5. Depending on the topology, the base torques, base speeds (at which the maximum torque

without flux weakening can be achieved), and maximum torques at maximum speed are slightly different. However, the overall performance of all four machines is comparable. Furthermore, the iron losses range for all four topologies are in the range of 20 W in low speeds to 60 W at the maximum speed.

The corresponding figures for the case with one PhOC in phase A are shown in Fig. 6. In order to limit the phase currents to the rated one, the amplitude of current in d- and q-axis plane is decreased based on the RF reported in Table II. Consequently, the maximum torque of the machines and also the maximum achievable speed using flux weakening are decreased. In this case, the maximum torque is 30% lower than the healthy case and the maximum speed is reduced to 4500 rpm.

By comparing corresponding losses maps in Fig. 5 and 6, it is observed that the loss ranges slightly increase for the case of one PhOC. However, it should be noticed that compared to the healthy case, the maximum speed is 25% lower. It means that in the faulty case, at much lower speeds the iron losses exceed the ones in the healthy case. Moreover, it is observed that the increase occurs at higher speed and also torque. In fact, under higher torque and speed, the armature reaction field starts to contribute more to the magnetic field distribution, while at low speeds the PM field is the dominant one. Thus, the magnetic field distortion due to the faults affects the iron losses especially at high speeds and torque.

Similar figures with two PhOCs in phase A1 and B2 are shown in Fig. 7. The currents are again decreased based on RF in Table II. Compared to the case with one PhOC, the maximum torque and torque at the maximum speed are further decreased, while the maximum speed is increased. In this case the loss range has increased considerably compared to the healthy case. The increase for the TW topologies is more pronounced than the DW ones. Again, the increase at high speeds and torques is more noticeable like the case with one PhOC. Similar figures can be obtained for other faults reported in Table II. However, for the sake of compactness, they are

Fig. 5. Iron losses at whole torque-speed plane with different topologies at the healthy case with MTPA and flux-weakening strategies

TABLE III

PERCENTAGE OF IRON LOSSES PER TOOTH SPAN WITH TWS AT 1000 RPM						
tooth number	1	2	3	4	5	6
1 PhOC	15%	20.9%	19.2%	12.7%	19%	13.1%
2 PhOC	14.3%	22.5%	13.4%	14.2%	22.1%	13.4%

not included in this paper.

A. Loss Distribution

In Fig. 8, loss distribution in the healthy condition and faulty case with one PhOC in phase A is illustrated. i_d and i_q are selected for having comparable output torque. Moreover, the losses are calculated for 1000 rpm. the iron losses are distributed evenly among the stator teeth and the periodicity of loss distribution is one tooth pitch (see Fig. 11 (a)). By contrast, with one PhOC fault, the iron loss concentration in some teeth and also some regions of the stator core is observed and the tooth-pitch periodicity of the loss distribution is lost. The percentage of iron losses which occurs in one tooth pitch span starting from the middle of slot with one or two PhOC is reported in Table III. Similar changes in the distribution of loss for the other faults can be observed.

VI. CONCLUSION

Iron losses of dual-star PMSMs under different PhOCs are investigated. A commercial PMSM machine designed for the power-steering application was selected for the study, while other machine topologies with comparable performance were derived from the original machine for the sake of comparison. It is observed that iron losses with PhOC faults and FTC method increase, particularly at high speeds, compared to the healthy case. It is found also that the PMSM with concentrated winding undergo higher increase in the iron loss. In this regard, PMSMs with DW can be a superior option for fault-tolerant applications compared to machines with TW, particularly for wide speed range applications. Moreover, the concentration of the iron losses in some teeth and stator yoke segments will occur under FTC method. Although just dual-star machines were studied in this paper, similar increase in the iron losses in other multi-phase machines under FTC methods is expected, as long as the balanced distribution of magnetomotive force and consequently magnetic loading cannot be maintained.

Fig. 6. Iron losses at whole torque-speed plane with different rotor topologies at the faulty case with one PhOC at phase A with reduced dq currents based on RF

Fig. 7. Iron losses at whole torque-speed plane with different rotor topologies at the faulty case with two PhOCs at phase A1 and B2 with reduced dq currents based on RF

Fig. 8. Iron loss distribution with $i_d = 0$ and $i_q = 155A$ with SPM rotor at 1000 rpm

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Abdolmajid Abedini Mohammadi received his B.Sc. and M.Sc. degrees in electrical engineering from Shahrekord University and Sharif University of Technology, both in Iran, in 2013 and 2015 respectively. From 2017 to 2018, he was an electrical engineer at the R&D department of Pars Generator Company, Tehran, Iran. He is currently with Brose Fahrzeugteile SE & Co. KG, Würzburg, Germany, within the Drives/Simulation Group as an Early-stage researcher (ESR) in the frame of the H2020 MSCA EID 2017-2021 research project INTERAC. Since 2018, he is a Ph.D. candidate at the BEAMS department of Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB), Brussels, Belgium. His research interests are modeling, design, and control of electrical machines, and in particular of permanent-magnet synchronous machines.

Adrian-Cornel Pop received the B.Sc. and M.Sc. degrees from the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, Cluj-Napoca, Romania, in 2009 and 2010, respectively, both in electrical engineering, and the Ph.D. degree in the frame work of a joint program between the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, and the Université Libre de Bruxelles, Brussels, Belgium, in 2012. He is first author or coauthor of some 20 scientific papers, 3 patents and one conference tutorial. He is currently with Brose Fahrzeugteile SE & Co. KG, Würzburg, Germany, within the Drives/Simulation Group. His current research is focused on optimal design for cost and performance of brushless AC and DC machines for automotive applications (i.e., power train, chassis, and thermal management) by means of multiphysics analysis starting from the customer-provided requirements and specifications. His past and current subjects of interest include design and optimization of electrical machines and drives (SRMs, PMSMs, and IMs), numerical methods, and hybrid and electrical vehicles.

Johan Gyselinck obtained his M.Sc. and PhD degree in electromechanical engineering from the Ghent University (Belgium) in 1991 and 2000 respectively. From 2000 till 2004 he was postdoctoral researcher and lecturer at the University of Liège (Belgium). Since 2004 he is professor at the Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB, Belgium). His main teaching and research topics are low-frequency magnetics (finite-element and analytical modelling, numerical methods), electrical machines and drives (modelling, simulation, design and experimental work), and renewables (wind and photovoltaics). He is (co-)author of some 300 journal and conference papers.